

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POLYMERIC FILMS OF KETOPROFEN TRANSDERMAL PATCHES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, an attempt was made to develop and evaluate transdermal matrix films of ketoprofen using ethyl cellulose, polyvinyl pyrrolidone and poly1-vinyl pyrrolidone-co-vinyl acetate (Copovidone) to achieve controlled release in order to minimize adverse effects associated with oral administration. Transdermal films of ketoprofen with EC alone and blends of EC: PVP and EC: Copovidone in different ratios of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 1:6 and 1:9 were prepared by by method of solvent casting on mercury surface. FTIR and DSC were studied to assess any interaction between the drug and the polymers. All prepared films were evaluated for physicochemical characteristics such as physical appearance, thickness and weight uniformity, folding endurance, water vapor transmission (WVT) studies, SEM analysis and drug content uniformity. *The in vitro* permeation studies through rat abdominal skin were

performed by using fabricated Keshary-Chien diffusion cell and obtained results were computed by using dissolution software PCP DISSO V3. The *in vitro* release data of all films were treated with various kinetic models such as Higuchi, first order, zero order and Korsmeyer-Peppas model. Further *in vivo* studies like anti-inflammatory, analgesic and skin irritation test were performed for selected EC: PVP and EC: Copovidone films. From the overall *in vitro* permeation Studies it could be concluded that the polymeric matrix-type transdermal films of ketoprofen prepared with the blends of hydrophobic (EC) and hydrophilic polymers (PVP and Copovidone) in different ratios holds potential for transdermal delivery which gives a slow and controlled release of drug up to 24 h. Further the present investigations revealed that the problems of ketoprofen on oral administration like gastric side effects can be

overcome by applying the drug topically in the form of transdermal film.

KEYWORDS: Transdermal drug delivery, Ketoprofen, Ethyl cellulose, Polyvinyl pyrrolidone, Poly1-vinyl pyrrolidone-co-vinyl acetate (Copovidone).

INTRODUCTION

In the past three decades, the treatment of an acute disease or a chronic illness has been mostly accomplished by delivery of drugs to patients using various conventional dosage forms like tablets, capsules, ointments, liquids, and injectables, as drug carriers. This type of drug delivery system is known to provide a prompt release of drug. Therefore, to achieve as well as to maintain the drug concentration within the therapeutically effective range needed for treatment, it is often necessary to take the conventional type of drug delivery systems several times a day. This results in a significant fluctuation of drug levels in the body. Further the conventional dosage forms used for the control of infection, pain and fertility may cause side effects like nausea, vomiting, gastric irritation and toxicity if they are consumed for long duration.^[1]

Novel drug delivery systems (NDDS) are capable of controlling the rate of drug delivery, sustaining the duration of therapeutic activity and/or targeting the delivery of drug to a particular tissue.^[2] TDDS constitutes one of the most important routes of NDDS due to its numerous advantages over conventional delivery methods including oral and parenteral route. As a result, the research into transdermal drug delivery has greatly increased over the past few years. This is evident from the remarkable achievements of pharmaceutical technologists who have made (TDDS) the most successful non-oral systemic drug delivery and also a highly successful commercial venture. The technology has a proven record of FDA approval since the first transdermal patch was approved in 1981 (Scopolamine patch).^[3]

Transdermal patches are adhesive, medicated, multi-layered dosage forms (TDDS) applied to the skin to deliver a set dose of medication through the skin into the bloodstream. They offer controlled, sustained release—lasting hours to days—bypassing first-pass metabolism, reducing side effects, and improving patient compliance for therapies like pain, nicotine replacement, and hormones.

Key Components of Transdermal Patches

Transdermal systems generally comprise the following

- **Backing Layer:** Protects the patch from the outside environment and prevents drug loss.
- **Drug Reservoir/Matrix:** Contains the drug in a matrix or liquid compartment.
- **Release-Controlling Membrane:** Regulates the rate of drug release (in reservoir systems).
- **Adhesive Layer:** Secures the patch to the skin and maintains intimate contact.
- **Release Liner (Liner):** Protects the adhesive layer during storage and is removed before application.

MATERIALS

Ketoprofen was kindly supplied by FDC limited, Mumbai.

Ethyl cellulose and polyvinyl pyrrolidone were purchased from CDH Laboratories and NR chemicals, Mumbai respectively. Poly (1-vinyl pyrrolidone co vinyl acetate) was procured from Sigma Aldrich Bengaluru. All other chemicals and solvents used were of analytical grade.

METHODS

Determination of λ max: Ketoprofen (100 mg) was dissolved in 100 ml of methanol and further 1 ml diluted serially with pH 7.4 phosphate buffer to obtain a desired concentration and subjected for UV scanning in the range of 200-400 nm using a double beam UV-VIS spectrophotometer. The absorption maxima of ketoprofen are obtained at 248 nm with a Characteristics peak in figure1.

FIG 1: UV Absorption maxima of ketoprofen.

FORMULATION OF MATRIX TYPE OF TRANSDERMAL SYSTEM: Matrix type transdermal films of ethyl cellulose containing ketoprofen were prepared initially by method of solvent casting on mercury surface.

Then films containing ketoprofen were prepared using blends of EC: PVP and EC: Copovidone

in different ratios as shown in **table 1**.

The polymers were weighed in requisite ratio and then dissolved in 4 ml chloroform. Dibutyl phthalate 30% w/w of polymer composition was used as plasticizer.

Then required amount of drug was added and stirred to get a homogeneous dispersion.

The dispersion (2 ml) was poured within a glass bangle (3.66 cm) on the surface of mercury in a petri dish.

SI. NO.	DRUG	BATCHES	EC: COPOVIDONE RATIOS
1	Ketoprofen	EC	1:0
2	Ketoprofen	EC: PVP	1:1
3	Ketoprofen	EC: PVP	1:2
4	Ketoprofen	EC: PVP	1:3
5	Ketoprofen	EC: PVP	1:6
6	Ketoprofen	EC: PVP	1:9
7	Ketoprofen	EC:Copovidone	1:1
8	Ketoprofen	EC:Copovidone	1:2
9	Ketoprofen	EC:Copovidone	1:3
10	Ketoprofen	EC:Copovidone	1:6
11	Ketoprofen	EC:Copovidone	1:9

- ❖ Ketoprofen was combined with Ethyl cellulose in 1:0 ratio in Formulation-1
- ❖ Formulation 2 to 6 are a combination of standard ketoprofen ratio of 1 and various ratio of PVP 1:9
- ❖ Formulation 7 to 11 are a combination of standard ketoprofen ratio of 1 and various ratio of COPOVIDONE 1:9

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DRUG EXCIPIENTS INCOMPATIBILITY STUDIES

FT-IR spectra of ketoprofen, ethyl cellulose and physical mixture of ketoprofen and ethyl cellulose.

Fig. 1: Ketoprofen.

Fig.2: Ethyl cellulose.

Fig. 3: Ketoprofen & EC.

- FT-IR spectra of ketoprofen, ethyl cellulose and physical mixture of ketoprofen and ethyl cellulose.
- From peaks obtained in FT-IR spectra of ketoprofen and ethyl cellulose, no drug excipient incompatibility was detected.

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

Table-2: Physical parameters and ketoprofen content in EC, EC: PVP and EC: COPOVIDONE transdermal patches.

Batches	Physical appearance	Weight*(mg)	Thickness*(μm)	Folding endurance*	Drug content*
EC	++	274.73 (\pm 0.611)	120.66 (\pm 2.082)	243.4 (\pm 1.140)	92.81% (\pm 1.032)
EC: PVP (1:1)	++	274.46 (\pm 1.137)	112.33 (\pm 1.528)	266.2 (\pm 1.643)	91.25% (\pm 1.669)
EC: PVP (1:2)	++	276.73 (\pm 1.159)	104.00 (\pm 1.732)	256.6 (\pm 1.673)	92.18% (\pm 1.506)
EC: PVP (1:3)	++	277.20 (\pm 0.800)	98.33 (\pm 0.577)	234.4 (\pm 2.510)	95.62% (\pm 1.273)
EC: PVP (1:6)	++	278.76 (\pm 0.602)	84.33 (\pm 1.528)	181.8 (\pm 2.387)	94.37% (\pm 0.919)
EC: PVP (1:9)	++	277.66 (\pm 1.060)	77.33 (\pm 3.215)	83.2 (\pm 1.304)	96.25% (\pm 2.531)
EC: COPOVIDONE (1:1)	++	277.30 (\pm 0.556)	105.33 (\pm 1.528)	254.2 (\pm 3.033)	94.06% (\pm 0.664)
EC: COPOVIDONE (1:2)	++	275.46 (\pm 0.873)	101.80 (\pm 1.852)	237.2 (\pm 2.588)	95.00% (\pm 1.810)
EC: COPOVIDONE (1:3)	++	278.26 (\pm 0.416)	91.66 (\pm 1.528)	239.2 (\pm 3.033)	93.43% (\pm 2.418)

EC: COPOVIDONE (1:6)	++	273.86 (\pm 1.343)	87.66 (\pm 1.52)	172.2 (\pm 1.483)	92.50% (\pm 2.574)
EC: COPOVIDONE (1:9)	++	276.46 (\pm 0.873)	70.66 (\pm 0.577)	65.8 (\pm 3.114)	93.125% (\pm 2.772)

The figure inside the parenthesis denotes the standard SD values.

* Average of three observation

++ Satisfactory.

Ketoprofen transdermal patches was subjected to Evaluation tests like Physical appearance, Weight variation, Thickness, Folding endurance and Drug content uniformity.

They were within the pharmacopoeial limits

DISSOLUTION STUDIES

Table-3: Mathematical modelling of and comparative kinetic values obtained from transdermal films of ketoprofen.

Time (h)	Cumulative percent of drug released (\pm SD, n=3)					
	EC	EC: PVP (1:1)	EC: PVP (1:2)	EC: PVP (1:3)	EC: PVP (1:6)	EC: PVP (1:9)
1	5.83 \pm 0.26	9.56 \pm 0.26	10.50 \pm 0.53	11.43 \pm 0.26	15.35 \pm 0.53	28.41 \pm 0.53
2	10.32 \pm 0.52	13.24 \pm 0.78	13.83 \pm 0.55	16.26 \pm 0.27	19.78 \pm 0.25	30.66 \pm 0.25
3	13.27 \pm 0.52	14.23 \pm 0.55	16.33 \pm 0.23	21.08 \pm 0.81	24.15 \pm 0.27	34.08 \pm 0.55
4	16.12 \pm 0.27	15.61 \pm 0.23	20.21 \pm 0.24	23.25 \pm 0.48	29.02 \pm 0.28	40.56 \pm 0.24
5	18.49 \pm 0.77	18.89 \pm 0.55	22.71 \pm 0.28	26.95 \pm 0.82	32.54 \pm 0.24	46.85 \pm 0.51
6	19.99 \pm 0.54	20.40 \pm 0.31	25.45 \pm 0.50	31.69 \pm 0.58	34.28 \pm 0.28	49.58 \pm 0.26
7	21.15 \pm 0.77	21.94 \pm 0.47	27.33 \pm 0.54	33.95 \pm 0.46	36.97 \pm 0.55	52.53 \pm 0.26
8	24.01 \pm 0.26	25.19 \pm 0.56	29.43 \pm 0.82	35.14 \pm 0.21	40.09 \pm 0.31	55.72 \pm 0.53
9	26.38 \pm 0.54	27.22 \pm 0.21	32.51 \pm 0.21	36.89 \pm 10.48	42.54 \pm 0.58	59.34 \pm 0.25
10	29.18 \pm 0.24	29.60 \pm 0.48	34.92 \pm 0.22	38.29 \pm 30.29	44.66 \pm 0.33	63.22 \pm 0.26
12	31.30 \pm 0.51	33.10 \pm 0.55	38.31 \pm 0.04	40.63 \pm 0.49	48.86 \pm 0.34	67.36 \pm 0.053
16	34.96 \pm 0.79	36.06 \pm 0.22	41.23 \pm 0.49	45.08 \pm 0.51	57.63 \pm 0.88	74.19 \pm 0.25
20	37.78 \pm 0.29	39.09 \pm 0.49	45.51 \pm 0.28	51.50 \pm 0.26	64.42 \pm 0.38	84.36 \pm 0.27

The release profile of ketoprofen from transdermal films was performed by using fabricated Keshary-Chien diffusion cell. The film (area 1.168 cm² = 10 mg of drug) was placed on rat abdominal skin and mounted between the donor and receptor compartment of the diffusion cell. The receptor compartment was filled with 30 ml of phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 previously equilibrated to 37 °C through the sampling port. The cell was placed in water bath maintained at 37 \pm 1°C on a magnetic stirrer and stirred magnetically at 50 rpm. At selected time intervals aliquots (1 ml) were removed and replaced with fresh diffusion media to maintain sink condition. The concentration of drug released at different time intervals was assayed spectrophotometrically at 248 nm against blank. The studies were carried out in triplicate. The

in vitro permeation results of all prepared films of ketoprofen were computed by using dissolution software PCP.

- In case of EC: PVP and EC: COPOVIDONE films, flux and drug release rate increased with the increase in the concentrations of hydrophilic polymers i, e., PVP and COPOLYVIDONE. The highest drug release was observed with EC: PVP 1:9 ratio (91.07%) and EC: COPOVIDONE1: 9 ratio (98.65%).
- The selected matrix systems (EC: PVP and EC: COPOVIDONE, at 1:9 ratio) showed significant anti-inflammatory ($p < 0.01$) and analgesic activities ($p < 0.01$) as compared with the control.

Figure-1: In vitro permeation rate of ketoprofen from EC films through rat abdominal skin (A)- without model fitting (B)- with model fitting.

Figure-2: In vitro permeation rate profile of ketoprofen from EC: PVP (1:1) films through rat abdominal skin (A) – Without model fitting (B) – with model fitting.

Figure-3: In vitro permeation rate profile of ketoprofen from EC: PVP (1:2) films through rat abdominal skin (A) -without model fitting (B) - with model fitting.

Figure-4: In vitro permeation rate profile of ketoprofen from EC: PVP (1:3) films through rat abdominal skin (A) -Without model fitting (B) -with model fitting.

Figure-5: In vitro permeation rate profile of ketoprofen from EC: PVP (1:6) films through rat abdominal skin (A) -without model fitting (B)-with model fitting.

Figure-6: In vitro permeation rate profile of ketoprofen from EC: PVP (1:9) films through rat abdominal skin (A)- without model fitting (B)-with model fitting.

Comparative *in vitro* permeation rate profiles of ketoprofen from EC films and EC: PVP films in different ratios through rat abdominal skin.

Figure-7: *In vitro* permeation rate profile of ketoprofen from EC: Copovidone (1:1) films through rat abdominal skin (a) without model fitting (b) with model fitting.

Figure-8: *In vitro* permeation rate profile of ketoprofen from EC: Copovidone (1:2) films through rat abdominal skin (a) without model fitting (b) with model fitting.

Figure-9: *In vitro* permeation rate profile of ketoprofen from EC: Copovidone (1:3) films through rat abdominal skin (a) without model fitting (b) with model fitting

Figure-10: *In vitro* permeation rate profile of ketoprofen from EC: Copovidone (1:6) films through rat abdominal skin (a) without model fitting (b) with model fitting.

Figure-11: *In vitro* permeation rate profile of ketoprofen from EC: Copovidone (1:9) films through rat abdominal skin (a) without model fitting (b) with model fitting.

Comparative *in vitro* permeation rate profiles of ketoprofen from EC and EC:Copovidone films in different ratios through rat abdominal skin.

FLUX AND PERMEABILITY COEFFICIENT DATA OF ALL TRANSDERMAL PATCHES OF KETOPROFEN

Batches	Flux ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{min}$)	Permeability coefficient (cm/ h)
EC	57.68	5.731×10^{-3}
EC: PVP (1:1)	74.08	6.018×10^{-3}
EC: PVP (1:2)	106.27	7.044×10^{-3}
EC: PVP (1:3)	121.84	7.935×10^{-3}
EC: PVP (1:6)	143.67	9.674×10^{-3}
EC: PVP (1:9)	156.98	12.920×10^{-3}
EC: COPOVIDONE (1:1)	120.78	6.406×10^{-3}

EC: COPOVIDONE (1:2)	113.32	7.761×10^{-3}
EC: COPOVIDONE (1:3)	125.57	8.787×10^{-3}
EC: COPOVIDONE (1:6)	127.93	11.134×10^{-3}
EC: COPOVIDONE (1:9)	168.03	13.74310^{-3}

The flux and permeability coefficient data of all transdermal films of ketoprofen were within limits.

Comparatively, EC: COPOVIDONE films showed higher flux and drug release than EC: PVP films.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The oral administration of ketoprofen often produces gastric irritation, and sometimes patients can develop ulceration and severe gastrointestinal bleeding. The transdermal route is an alternative route of administration for such drugs. In the present study, attempts were made to develop and evaluate transdermal matrix films of ketoprofen employing various polymers to achieve controlled release in order to minimize adverse effects associated with oral administration.

- Pre formulation studies on ketoprofen were found in accordance with the reported literature limits
- FT-IR and DSC studies conformed no interaction b/w the drug and polymers.
- Thin, flexible, smooth and transparent films were obtained with EC alone, blends of EC PVP and EC: COPOVIDONE films.
- Water vapour transmission (WVT) through drug free transdermal films followed zero order kinetics.
- All the films prepared with the blends of EC: PVP and EC: COPOVIDONE showed sustained and prolonged release of ketoprofen up to 24 h compared to films prepared with EC alone.

In case of EC: PVP and EC: COPOVIDONE films, flux and drug release rate increased with the increase in the concentrations of hydrophilic polymers i, e., PVP and COPOLYVIDONE. The highest drug release was observed with EC: PVP 1:9 ratio (91.07%) and EC: COPOVIDONE1: 9 ratio (98.65%).

- The selected matrix systems (EC: PVP and EC: COPOVIDONE, at 1:9 ratio) showed significant anti-inflammatory ($p < 0.01$) and analgesic activities ($p < 0.01$) as compared with the control.
- The selected ketoprofen transdermal films did not show skin irritation on rats, ascertaining their safety for topical application.

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